
BC-SIM-TN-017

SIMBIO-SYS Target-Oriented Observation Strategies

Valentina Galluzzi¹, Pasquale Palumbo¹, Fabrizio Capaccioni¹, Cristina Re², Gianrico Filacchione¹, Gabriele Cremonese², Livio Agostini¹, Cecilia Tubiana¹, Adriano Tullio², Michele Zusi¹, Emanuele Simioni², Alain Doressoundiram³, Mathieu Vincendon⁴

¹INAF-ISTITUTO ASTROFISICA E PLANETOLOGIA SPAZIALI, VIA FOSSO DEL CAVALIERE 100, 00133, ROME, ITALY

²INAF-OSSERVATORIO ASTRONOMIC DI PADOVA, VICOLO OSSERVATORIO 5,35122, PADUA, ITALY

³OBSERVATOIRE DE PARIS - PSL, LABORATOIRE D'ÉTUDES SPATIALES ET D'INSTRUMENTATION EN ASTROPHYSIQUE (LESIA), 92195 MEUDON CEDEX, FRANCE

⁴INSTITUT D'ASTROPHYSIQUE SPATIALE, CNRS / UNIVERSITE PARIS SUD, 91405, ORSAY, FRANCE

Index

INDEX	1
EDITING	3
CHANGE LOG	3
1 INTRODUCTION	4
1.1 SCOPE	4
1.2 REFERENCE DOCUMENT	4
1.3 ACRONYMS	4
1.4 DOCUMENT FORMAT AND REPOSITORY	4
1.5 DOCUMENT ORGANIZATION	5
2 SIMBIO-SYS CHANNELS OBSERVATION STRATEGIES	6
3 BASICS OF SIMBIO-SYS CHANNELS OBSERVATION CAPABILITIES	6
3.1 HRIC	6
3.2 STC	7
3.3 VIHI	8
4 MEASUREMENTS STRUCTURE	9
5 TARGET-ORIENTED OBSERVATIONS RATIONALE	9
5.1 OBSERVATION MODE	10
5.1.1 <i>HRIC_MODE</i>	11
5.1.2 <i>STC_MODE</i>	11
5.1.3 <i>VIHI_MODE</i>	12
5.2 TRUE ANOMALY RANGE	12
5.2.1 <i>HRIC_MTA</i>	12
5.2.2 <i>STC_MTA</i>	12
5.2.3 <i>VIHI_MTA</i>	13
5.3 INSIGHTS INTO PERISIDE OBSERVATIONS (MTA = 90° – 270°)	13
5.3.1 <i>HRIC at periside</i>	13
5.3.2 <i>STC at periside</i>	13
5.3.3 <i>VIHI at periside</i>	13
5.4 INSIGHTS INTO APOSIDE OBSERVATIONS (MTA = 270° – 90°)	14
5.4.1 <i>HRIC at aposide</i>	14
5.4.2 <i>STC at aposide</i>	14
5.4.3 <i>VIHI at aposide</i>	14
5.5 OBSERVATION PLANNING CRITERIA	15
5.5.1 <i>HRIC criteria</i>	15
5.5.2 <i>STC criteria</i>	17
5.5.3 <i>VIHI criteria</i>	18
5.6 TARGET RANKING	18
6 CONCLUDING REMARKS	19
6.1 HRIC	19
6.2 STC	21
6.3 VIHI	22
7 APPENDIX	23
7.1 HRIC OFF-POINTING FOR TARGET LONGITUDE COVERAGE	23

Document	BC-SIM-TN-017
Date	14/07/2025
Issue.Revision	1.0
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.15880226
Page	2 of 24

7.2	HRIC STEREO-DTM STRATEGY	23
8	ACKNOWLEDGMENTS.....	24

Editing

Prepared by:	
	Valentina Galluzzi
	Pasquale Palumbo
	Fabrizio Capaccioni
	Cristina Re
	Gianrico Filacchione
Revised by:	
	Livio Agostini
	Cecilia Tubiana
	Adriano Tullo
	Michele Zusi
	Emanuele Simioni
	Alain Doressoundiram
	Mathieu Vincendon
Authorized by:	
	Gabriele Cremonese

Change Log

Issue	Revision	Date	Affected Pages	Change description
1	0	14/07/2025	All	First Issue

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

This document outlines the target-oriented observational strategies employed by SIMBIO-SYS for maximizing scientific returns during Mercury observations.

1.2 Reference Document

- [RD.1] BC-SIM-TN-003 – Reports and Notes Layout and Flow – Version 3.1, [10.5281/zenodo.14505747](https://zenodo.org/records/14505747)
- [RD.2] BepiColombo’s Targets and Georeference Systems Baseline Recommendations – Version 2

1.3 Acronyms

APH	Aphelion
CP	Cold Poles
DTM	Digital Terrain Model
DV	Data Volume
GM	Global Mapping
HY	Mercury Year
HP	Hot Poles
HRIC	High-Resolution Imaging Channel
MTP	Mid-Term Planning
PHE	Perihelion
SIMBIO-SYS	Spectrometer and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYSTEM
STC	STEREO imaging Channel
STP	Short-Term Planning
TGSTG	Targets and Georeference Systems Task Group
TL	Target List
TO	Target-Oriented
TOO	Target-Oriented Observations
VIHI	Visible-Infrared Hyperspectral Imager

1.4 Document Format and Repository

This document is compliant with the SIMBIO-SYS Report and Note Layout and Flow [RD.1] and will be archived on the SIMBIO-SYS ZENODO community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/simbio-sys>), on the INAF Open Access repository, and the SIMBIO-SYS Team Archive.

1.5 Document organization

This document is structured to provide a comprehensive and operationally useful description of SIMBIO-SYS target-oriented observation strategies. After introducing the document scope and relevant references, the following sections are organized as follows:

- **Section 2** describes the overall observation strategy adopted by the SIMBIO-SYS instrument suite, distinguishing between Global Mapping and Target-Oriented Observations, with an emphasis on the latter.
- **Section 3** outlines the basic observational capabilities and operational constraints of each SIMBIO-SYS channel (HRIC, STC, VIHI), including their nominal acquisition modes and expected performance during different mission phases.
- **Section 4** introduces the Measurement Structure, linking each observation mode to specific science requirements through a traceability matrix.
- **Section 5** details the rationale behind Target-Oriented Observations, including the structure of the Target List, observation mode selection criteria, season-dependent constraints (expressed via Mercury True Anomaly ranges), and planning criteria per instrument. Subsections cover both periside and aposide strategies.
- **Section 6** provides channel-specific concluding remarks and summarizes key strategic guidelines for HRIC, STC, and VIHI, including resource management and long-term planning considerations.
- **Section 7 (Appendix)** includes implementation notes and special planning strategies. It currently comprises: 1) a dedicated analysis of HRIC off-nadir pointing strategies required for longitudinal coverage of selected targets across multiple Mercury years, and 2) an additional section detailing HRIC-specific stereo acquisition strategies for high-resolution Digital Terrain Model generation. This includes potential conflicts, geometric considerations, and future planning adaptations.

Each section is designed to support both scientific prioritization and operational feasibility, ensuring traceability between mission goals, planning logic, and instrument capabilities.

2 SIMBIO-SYS Channels Observation Strategies

SIMBIO-SYS observation strategies are classified into Global Mapping (GM) and Target-Oriented Observations (TOO) observations. This document describes the TOO rationale.

- The High-Resolution Imaging Channel (HRIC) can provide only TOO with panchromatic or color filters.
- The Visible-Infrared Hyperspectral Imager (VIHI) can provide GM and higher spatial and/or spectral resolution TOO.
- The STereo imaging Channel (STC) can provide GM observations in stereo mode and TOO in color mode or increase stereo-mode vertical accuracy in challenging areas.

3 Basics of SIMBIO-SYS channels observation capabilities

A high-level description of SIMBIO-SYS channel observation capabilities is given in this section. For more detailed information refer to Cremonese et al. 2010 and instrument design description documents.

3.1 HRIC

The detector area is split into 4 sections, each one below 4 pass-band filters (Fig. 1). The continuous coverage of the observed surface is guaranteed along-track (latitude) by acquiring images with an appropriate repetition time (i.e., the time between two acquisitions avoiding gaps along-track) while the coverage across-track (longitude) is allowed by observations at the following orbits.

Filters central wavelength and bandwidth are:

- **PAN**: 650/500
- **F550**: 550/40
- **F750**: 750/40
- **F880**: 880/40

Figure 1. HRIC detector scheme illustrating the four pass-band filters used for imaging.

HRIC acquisition impact can be flexible via: 1) tuning the ground sampling by applying **binning** (2×2, 4×4, or 8×8), 2) applying **windowing** (which is not necessarily linked to filter dimension and position), and 3) **compression** (allowing to tune the data volume, with an impact on image quality). We have two nominal working modes:

- **PAN**, when the readout is done on the 640×2048 pixel window below the panchromatic filter.
- **COL**, when the three areas below the three color filters (nominally, 384×2048 pixels each) are acquired.

Some constraints apply due to H/W limitation in detector readout rate and a detailed description is reported in the UM. These constraints bring to the following limitations in the nominal mission (first Earth year):

- **COIL** mode can be used unbinned on the orbit's aposide, while we need 2x2 binning close to the periherm.
- **PAN** mode can always be used unbinned.

During mission extension (until the second Earth year after MOI) the issue worsens due to MPO orbit evolution (i.e., lower periherm, implying lower repetition times on periside):

- **COIL** mode can be used unbinned on the orbit aposide; on periside, even with 2x2 binning, we cannot guarantee the coverage in latitude around the periherm.
- **PAN** mode cannot guarantee latitude coverage towards the end of the extended mission close to the periside; 2x2 binning would be needed.

In **all cases**, when binning is needed, the constraint can be reduced or removed by reducing the swath (windowing across-track), with the drawback of further reducing the capability of coverage in longitude).

3.2 STC

STC is a push frame camera divided in two sub-channel, oriented at $\pm 20^\circ$ with respect to nadir, focusing on a single-detector. The two optical channels of STC allow photogrammetric capabilities to reconstruct the surface of Mercury in three dimensions. STC will acquire the entire Mercury surface with 2 panchromatic filters operating in stereo mode and with other 4 color filters (Fig. 2), centered in blue (420nm), green (550 nm), red (750 nm) and near-infrared (920 nm) parts of the spectrum will perform TOO.

The windowing applied to the FPA allowed to command the specific areas of each filter. The windows are 896 pixel wide by 384 pixel high for panchromatic filters and 64 pixel for other filters. In both cases, only 768 pixel cross track will be nominally used for the acquisitions. The width of the windows could also be reduced in order to optimize data volume when a certain data redundancy is met. During the stereo GM phase, that will be performed in the first six months of the nominal mission, the entire surface of the planet will be fully covered by both PAN filters.

The GM will be optimized in terms of DV both reducing the filters windows and skipping orbit acquisitions constraining a minimum overlapping between consecutive orbits (15% to guarantee good mosaicking performances).

The second six months of the nominal mission will be devoted to TOO. The target strategy will consider the use of the four broad band filters mainly

Start-End Rows		Vert Dim
2016	576px (strip 9) 1471px (strip 22)	
	F920	64px
1953 1808		
	F550	64px
1745 1610		
	PANL	384px
1227 820		
	PANH	384px
437 303		
192:319 (strips 3,4)	F420	64px
163 WinX 100 95		
	F750	64px
(0,0)	896px	

Figure 2 Focal Plane Assembly of STC. Vertical coordinates are expressed in pixels. Horizontal coordinates are expressed in pixels and in strips (1 strip = 64 pixels). (From Cremonese et al, 2020)

during the Aphelion (APH) season (higher spatial resolution associated with lower incidence angles at low latitudes).

During the Terminator ranges, STC will consider also the acquisitions of areas with better illumination conditions with respect the APH ranges. In particular during the APH, at low Latitudes the incidence angles will be not optimal for 3D reconstruction where we meet better illumination during Terminator. Better illumination conditions mean higher DTM accuracy.

STC will operate the targeting mode mainly with color filters but some targets will be considered with panchromatic filters in order to improve the accuracy of the DTMs for some specific areas.

Ultimately, some color acquisitions will be also considered during the GM phase to take advantage of the skipped orbit with panchromatic images.

Summarizing, the two nominal working modes of STC will be:

- **PAN:** when the readout is done on the 896 (across) × 384 (along) pixel window below the panchromatic filter to perform stereo acquisitions.
- **COL:** when the four areas below the four color filters (nominally, 896×64 pixels each) are acquired to perform target observations.

3.3 VIHI

VIHI is an imaging spectrometer which associate at each spatial pixel a full spectrum in the spectral range 400-2000 nm distributed over 256 spectral pixel (spectral sampling of 6.25 nm). Spatial pixels are acquired one line at a time, a line being composed of 256 pixel. A line is the projection of the VIHI instantaneous field of view on the surface of Mercury. Thus, a single acquisition is a matrix of 256×256 (spatial x spectral) pixel called “frame”. The optical system projects the frame on a 256×256 MCT detector. A 2D image is built in time, as the projection of the VIHI field of view moves with the S/C motion over the Mercury surface (pushbroom operation). An image is then a collection of subsequent frames. The final product (assembled on ground) is a 3D matrix (Cube) containing both spatial (2D) and spectral (1D) information.

The 256 spatial pixels can be binned 2× or 4× to reduce the DV and to comply with the scientific requirements of the mission. To guarantee a square pixel the above binning (Across track) has to be associated to an Along Track binning (2× or 4× binning of subsequent frames).

The 256 spectral pixels can be binned 2× or 4× again to reduce DV. If we apply binning, we degrade the spectral resolution reducing to 128 (2×) or 64 (4×) spectral pixels. To maintain high spectral resolution still reducing to 128 the number of spectral pixels we can select a spectral window.

The standard way of operating the instrument at Mercury will be in either GM mode (Global Mapping) or TO Mode (Target-Oriented).

In **GM mode** the instrument will be operated to maintain an average nominal spatial sampling of 400m on ground. Thus, as the orbit is not circular, we shall need to change binning mode according to the orbital position (binning 2× or 4×). Also, the spectral resolution will be degraded by applying a 2× binning (spectral sampling 12.5 nm).

In **TO mode**, the default commanding mode is to operate at maximum spectral and spatial sampling, that is, no binning neither in spatial nor in spectral direction.

4 Measurements Structure

Based on the above statements we consider the measurement structure in table 1 as the baseline framework for SIMBIO-SYS observational planning. The same structure has been used in the Traceability Matrix (TMX) to build science question-related measurements.

Table 1. SIMBIO-SYS Measurement Structure

	Channel	Measurement Type	Source	Mode	Requirements
A	SIM_STC	global stereo-imaging	global mapping	PAN	Global mapping in stereo mode at average spatial sampling (60 m/px)
B	SIM_VIHI	global hyperspectral mapping	global mapping	GM	Global mapping at average spatial sampling (400 m/px) and nominal spectral sampling (12.5 nm/band)
C	SIM_HRIC	high-resolution imaging of targets	targets	PAN	Panchromatic observation of a target.
D	SIM_HRIC	high-resolution color-imaging of targets	targets	COL	Multi-filter observation of the same target.
E	SIM_HRIC	high-resolution stereo-DTM of targets	targets	PAN	Off-nadir pointing of at least one observation in addition to the nominal nadir panchromatic observation of the same target.
F	SIM_HRIC	support to STC stereo-imaging at high-latitudes for targets	targets	PAN	Regional coverage at lower resolution at Lat. higher than $\pm 70^\circ$.
G	SIM_STC	color-imaging of targets	targets	COL	Multi-filter observation of the same target.
H	SIM_STC	stereo-imaging of targets	targets	PAN	Stereo observation of a target to increase vertical accuracy.
I	SIM_VIHI	spectral mapping of targets	targets	SPT/THM	High-spatial and/or spectral resolution of targets.

Other special measurements (e.g., terrains phase function measurement) needs dedicated pointing profile and shall be considered at operational level on a case-by-case basis.

5 Target-Oriented Observations Rationale

TARGET: Any feature of interest on the surface of Mercury that, when imaged at certain conditions, will help answering one or more science questions defined in the TMX, and that needs to be observed at better observation conditions than those already provided by the SIMBIO-SYS global coverage campaign or by MESSENGER.

Needed TOO are defined in the **Target List (TL)**. Each target in the TL has attributes that indicate **ideal conditions** to observe it and maximize the scientific return. The attributes are defined in Table 2 and include all the required fields as recommended by BepiColombo's Targets and Georeference Systems Task Group (TGSTG) [RD.2].

TABLE 2. TGSTG TARGETS ATTRIBUTE TABLE STRUCTURE

Attribute category	Attribute name	Data type	Examples	SIMBIO-SYS usage
Target name	TARGET_ID	text	SIM_<NNNNNN>	YES
Location	QUAD	text	H-07	YES
	CEN_LAT	double	22.19829132	YES
	CEN_LON	double	-140.74582541	YES
	MAX_LAT	double	22.88336326	YES
	MAX_LON	double	-140.3429153	YES
	MIN_LAT	double	21.61293635	YES

	MIN_LON	double	-141.0529461	YES
Observing conditions	INC_RANGE	range (text)	0-90	YES
	EMI_RANGE	range (text)	0-5	no
	PHA_RANGE	range (text)	0-90	no
	LOCAL_TIME	time	13:20:00	no
Instrument and sub-units	HRIC_MODE	text	PAN	YES
	STC_MODE	text	COL	YES
	VIHI_MODE	text	SPT	YES
	MER_TIS	text	NO	no
	MER_TIR	text	YES	no
	MIXS	text	YES	no
	BELA	text	NO	no
	PHEBUS	text	YES	no
	HRIC_MTA	range (text)	90-270 (periside)	YES
	STC_MTA	range (text)	135-225 (aphelion)	YES
	VIHI_MTA	range (text)	0-360 (all seasons)	YES
	TIS_MTA	range (text)	270-90 (aposide)	no
	TIR_MTA	range (text)	225-315 (terminator D2N)	no
	MIXS_MTA	range (text)	315-45 (perihelion)	no
BELA_MTA	range (text)	45-135 (terminator N2D)	no	
PHEBUS_MTA	Range (text)	0 (no observations)	no	
Science classification	CATEGORY	text (1 word)	VOLCANISM	YES
	TYPE	text (2 words)	COMPOUND VENT	YES
	RANK	integer	1-5	YES
	SCI_RATIO	text (250 char)	explanatory text	YES
	LIT_REF	text	DOI1; DOI2; etc.	YES
Author	AUTHOR	text	SIMBIO-SYS Team	YES

The feasibility of each observation as described by the TL attributes depends on available resolution during BC orbit and illumination conditions at Mercury. This makes `CHANNEL_MODE` and `CHANNEL_MTA` the most constraining attributes. **In the TL, overlapping and nested targets are allowed and required, as long as they need different observation mode (e.g. HRIC_MODE) and/or MTA range conditions (e.g., HRIC_MTA).**

5.1 Observation Mode

SIMBIO-SYS can make science observations only at dayside. Hence, `INC_RANGE` is always set to 0°-90°. When a channel is selected for targeting, `HRIC_MODE` indicates the observation mode, where `PAN` is for panchromatic observations, and `COL` is for color observations as explained above. `PAN` and `COL` modes only apply to the imagers (i.e., HRIC and STC), while for VIHI the observation mode can be either `THM` for observations aiming to measure thermal emission from the surface, or `SPT` for those planned to infer mineralogy.

5.1.1 HRIC_MODE

- When **HRIC_MODE** = **PAN** we prefer observations that enhance the surface morphology. Such conditions are reached with high incidence angles in the range of 40°-85°.
- When **HRIC_MODE** = **COL**, we prefer observations that enhance the surface albedo. Such conditions are reached with low incidence angles in the range of 0°-45°.

The reasons for adopting an overlap of 5 deg in incidence angle between the two observation modes are explained below in the *Observation Planning Criteria* paragraph.

When a surface feature requires different kinds of observations, nested targets are created on the feature, one asking for **COL**, the other for **PAN**.

The previous conditions are resumed in table 3 and an example is provided in figure 3.

Figure 3. Hollows as imaged by NASA MESSENGER MDIS/NAC: a) EN1034982894M, 41 m/pixel, 2° incidence angle. b) EN1010125026M, 23 m/pixel, 49° incidence angle. c) EN0250767456M, 18 m/pixel, 77° incidence angle.

5.1.2 STC_MODE

- When **STC_MODE** = **PAN** we prefer observations that support high accuracy DTMs. Such conditions are reached with high incidence angles in the range of 35°-75°.
- When **STC_MODE** = **COL**, we prefer observations that enhance the surface albedo. Such conditions are reached with low incidence angles in the range of 0°-45°.

Similarly to HRIC, an overlap between incidence angle conditions exists between the two modes. This is further explained in the *Observation Planning Criteria* paragraph.

When a surface feature requires different kinds of observations, nested targets are created on the feature, one asking for **COL**, the other for **PAN**. The previous conditions are resumed in table 3.

TABLE 3. HRIC_MODE AND STC_MODE SUN INCIDENCE ANGLE CONDITIONS

	HRIC_MODE		STC_MODE	
	PAN	COL	PAN	COL
SUN_INC	40°-85°	0°-45°	35°-75°	0°-45°

SUN_INC: sun incidence angle

5.1.3 VIHI_MODE

- When **VIHI_MODE** = **THM** we prefer observations that enhance the contribution of the surface thermal emission. At the same time we need also to compare the signal when thermal emission is negligible. The above requests translate in observation of the same target both at APH and Perihelion (PHE) seasons.
- When **VIHI_MODE** = **SPT** we prefer observations devoted to study the mineralogy of the surface. This is achieved in the MTA range of the APH season.

5.2 True Anomaly Range

Given the MPO's mission design, dayside observations can be achieved both at periside (MTA = 90°-270°) and aposide (MTA = 270°-90°). For targeted observations, our channels will operate as follows.

5.2.1 HRIC_MTA

- When **HRIC_MTA** = 90-270 periside observations are preferred.
- When **HRIC_MTA** = 270-90 aposide observations are preferred.
- When **HRIC_MTA** = 0-360 any season is acceptable, but in case of conflicts **periside has the priority**.

For a few cases, we also consider:

- **HRIC_MTA** = 90-180 for periside observations with illumination from the west.
- **HRIC_MTA** = 180-270 for periside observations with illumination from the east.
- **HRIC_MTA** = 270-360 for aposide observations with illumination from the west.
- **HRIC_MTA** = 0-90 for aposide observations with illumination from the west.

Or combined ranges like:

- **HRIC_MTA** = 90-180 ; 270-360 for any observation with illumination from the west.
- **HRIC_MTA** = 0-90 ; 180-270 for any observation with illumination from the east.

The previous conditions are resumed in table 4.

TABLE 4. HRIC_MTA SEASONAL CONDITIONS

	HRIC_MTA						
	90-270	270-90	90-180	180-270	270-360	0-90	0-360
OBS_SIDE	periside	aposide	periside	periside	aposide	aposide	any
SUN_DIR	any	any	west	east	west	east	any
PIX_RES	5-10	10-20	5-10	5-10	10-20	10-20	5-20

OBS_SIDE: observation side (aposide/periside); SUN_DIR: sun direction (from west/east); PIX_RES: unbinned pixel resolution range (m/pixel)

5.2.2 STC_MTA

- When **STC_MTA** = 135-225 APH season observations are preferred. These observations are specifically for **COL** observations or **PAN** re-observation after GM to improve DTM accuracy.
- When **STC_MTA** = 90-270 periside observations are preferred. These observations are specifically for **COL** mode.

- When **STC_MTA** = 45–90; 270–315 terminator apside observations are preferred. These are indicated to improve the accuracy of the DTMs, specifically in areas where optimal illumination conditions during GM are not met (i.e., **cold poles**).

5.2.3 VIHI_MTA

- When **VIHI_MTA** = 135–225 APH season observations are preferred. This is the range where the majority of VIHI observations will be performed.
- When **VIHI_MTA** = 315–45 PHE season observations are preferred.
- When **VIHI_MTA** = 0–360 Any season is acceptable.

5.3 Insights into Periside Observations (MTA = 90° – 270°)

Due to MPO's orbital evolution (periherm lowers, apoherm gets higher, semimajor axis remains constant, and periherm, which initially is at about 16°N, shifts southward) periside observations' characteristics are variable throughout the mission duration.

5.3.1 HRIC at periside

periside observations allow high-resolution imaging with ground sampling ranging from about **5 m/pixel to about 11 m/pixel** (at periherm and poles, respectively), with issues in longitude coverage. Indeed, in a latitude range of about $\pm 55^\circ$, the swath is not large enough to allow surface coverage in longitude with the following orbits. To fill the gap between two orbits, with the same solar azimuth, the following opportunity is after 2 Mercury years (HY), and when close to the equator, at least 3 passages are needed to complete longitude coverage, i.e. 4 HY after the first observation. It has to be noted that ***the need re-observe a target 2 and 4 HY later implies the need to develop a long-term planning and that those observations shall be considered high priority.***

A discussion on the requirements to implement efficiently the longitude coverage in following transit is discussed in the appendix of this document.

HRIC will favor periside observations for small targets that can be resolved only at resolutions higher than 10 m/pixel (e.g., **CATEGORY = HOLLOW**s).

5.3.2 STC at periside

Periside observations represent the **majority of STC acquisitions**, with ground resolution ranging from < 50 m/pixel at low latitudes to about 100 m/pixel at high latitudes.

The GM phase will be completed over approximately two full aphelion seasons, within **STC_MTA** = 138–222 (covering half of APH0, all of APH1, and the remaining part of APH2).

These same ranges also offer an opportunity for targeted operations in **COL** mode, by exploiting orbits that were skipped during the GM phase. **STC_MTA** = 135–225 generally provides favorable illumination and ground resolution conditions for multi-filter color observations (**COL** mode) and the period devoted to this kind of acquisitions (targeting) will be concentrated on the last two aphelia. However, periside observations within **STC_MTA** = 90–270 offer the possibility to further **COL** observations since favorable illumination are met.

5.3.3 VIHI at periside

The phases when most of the VIHI channel activity are focused are the **APH seasons**. This is valid for GM (although the intrinsic spatial sampling of VIHI would allow to cover areas of the surface at

the required spatial resolution for GM, also from aposide) and even more for TOO which require highest spatial sampling. Most of the VIHI target will then have $VIHI_MTA = 135-225$.

Nonetheless few scientific objectives require that observations will be carried out also in both Terminator seasons (Periside and Aposide) and thus will have $VIHI_MTA = 0-360$:

Coverage of PSR targets over a full Mercury year. In this case we need to follow the yearly evolution of the illuminated, and at the same time, of the shadowed regions of each target to accurately evaluate the extension of the PSR itself at several solar azimuth angles. Thus, the targets associated to **TYPE = PSR CRATER** will be selected whenever the opportunity will arise (meaning that the target will be observed several times).

Photometric response of Mercury' surface. Observing the same area at different solar phase angles is of interest as it allows to derive the phase curve which describes how the brightness of a surface varies with varying phase angle. This knowledge in turn will allow to derive, by means of radiative transfer models, the spectral albedo, a quantity describing the intrinsic reflectance of a medium at standard illumination and observation conditions. We shall identify a set of calibration targets (mainly of **CATEGORY = TERRAINS**) which should be observed throughout the HY to characterize as much as possible their brightness Vs. phase angle and to extend previous MESSENGER derivation. So the targets associated to **CATEGORY = TERRAINS** will be selected whenever the opportunity will arise (meaning that the target will be observed several times).

5.4 Insights into Aposide Observations (MTA = 270° – 90°)

5.4.1 HRIC at aposide

Aposide observations allow ground sampling ranging from about **11 m/pixel to 20 m/pixel** (at poles and apoherm, respectively). In this case, no issues with coverage are found, as there is enough cross-track overlap between footprints at all latitudes. HRIC will exploit aposide observations to acquire quick context mosaics of large features (e.g., *impact basins*), both in COL or PAN.

A drawback in aposide observations is given by the power limitation in the PH seasons that impose some constraints in observations.

5.4.2 STC at aposide

STC will exploit aposide observations (i.e., $STC_MTA=45-90$ and $STC_MTA=270-315$) to fill in gaps from the GM phase and to re-observe areas previously acquired under not optimal lighting conditions for stereo reconstruction (e.g., low solar incidence at the cold poles). Some PAN observations, within the same ranges, could be requested for multi-angles target observations requesting specific off-pointing maneuvers. To achieve this, flexible planning and the allocation of a dedicated number of acquisitions will be necessary.

5.4.3 VIHI at aposide

For the terminator seasons occurring at aposide the considerations developed for periside are still valid and will not be repeated here.

In addition, during the PHE season, the planet is closer to the Sun, the orbital speed is slower and the distance from the surface is larger than in the APH season. This means that for a target of similar optical properties and at the same latitude we shall have more signal in input and could use a longer integration time; the combination of these conditions will allow to obtain spectra with better Signal

to Noise Ratio albeit with a lower spatial resolution. For the PSR this means that will be available an higher flux of scattered light from the illuminated part of the craters' rims which in turn will give better conditions to detect the icy deposits' spectral features in the non-directly illuminated area. The changing heliocentric distance means also that the solar apparent size changes as a function of MTA (from 1.15° at APH to 1.76° at PHE) causing an increase of the penumbras projected on the surface. Such effect will give a further margin to operate VIHI from terminator to PHE seasons. In addition, the closeness to the Sun implies that the surface at the PHE will reach maximum temperatures which can be detected by the thermal radiance in the VIHI spectral range.

Observations of targets at Aposide will serve the following objectives:

- *PSR and Photometric targets over a full Mercury year.* These targets (as described in the periside chapter) need to be observed throughout the year thus will be characterized by **VIHI_MTA = 0-360**. Thus, the targets associated to **TYPE = PSR CRATER** will be selected whenever the opportunity will arise (meaning that the target will be observed several times).
- *Low reflectance regions observations.* Several selected regions, like LRM, display an intrinsic dark appearance; their low reflectance is further enhanced by low angle solar illumination. There could be the necessity to improve coverage of some targets in the PHE season to take advantage of better illumination conditions.
- *Sampling of Surface Temperatures.* During the PHE season the surface temperatures can be as high as to be detected by VIHI in the spectral range 1.5-2.0 μm. Although the thermal emission could complicate somewhat the discernment of spectral features in that spectral range, nonetheless would allow to measure surface temperature with a slightly better spatial resolution than MERTIS. In this case the **VIHI_MTA = 315-45** and **VIHI_MODE = THM** will indicate that the selected target has to be observed both at APH and at PHE. Priority here will be assigned to targets with latitude ±40°.

5.5 Observation Planning Criteria

5.5.1 HRIC criteria

Given the low (almost null) inclination of Mercury's axis, we divide the planet into two main regions as shown in figure 4:

1. **REGION 1:** contains equatorial latitudes up to ±40°.
2. **REGION 2:** contains high latitudes higher than ±40°.

In general, three observation opportunities are always possible at each target at a given longitude for each solar day (i.e., 2 HY, 6 Earth months). The three opportunities are mostly structured as follows:

1. One opportunity at periside with incidence from the east.
2. One opportunity at aposide with incidence either from the east or the west.
3. One opportunity at periside with incidence from the west.

An exception is given by longitudes ±80°-±100° (**cold poles**) where we find:

1. One opportunity at aposide with incidence from the east.

Figure 4. HRIC Planning regions.

2. One opportunity at periside with either from the east or the west.
3. One opportunity at aposide with incidence from the west.

This is outlined by the plots in figures 5 and 6.

5.5.1.1 Region 1: Equatorial Latitudes

Region 1 (R1) allows for **seasonal observations** as it is characterized by the consistent availability of suitable illumination conditions for **COL** observations, ensuring that desired observational criteria are always met during at least one of the three available observing opportunities (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Plots of boresight longitude vs. incidence angle, where positive and negative incidence angles are for sun from the east and west, respectively. The green horizontal areas indicate incidence ranges ideal for COL, blue ones for PAN. Red areas indicate hot poles (HP), grey areas are for cold poles (CP). Plots are centered a different latitudes: a) Equatorial; b) 20°N/S; c) 40°N/S

- **Overlap conditions:** The overlap region, defined between incidence angles of 40° and 45° (Tab. 3), ensures optimal flexibility in the observation of equatorial targets located at Mercury's **hot poles (HP)** during APH. Specifically:
 - Setting the minimum **PAN** incidence angle strictly at 45° would exclude the visibility of equatorial targets situated at HP.
 - Conversely, imposing the maximum **COL** incidence angle strictly at 40° would restrict the observation of these targets exclusively to the PHE critical season (i.e., $MTA = 0^\circ \pm 10^\circ$), significantly limiting observation opportunities.

Therefore, the established overlap (40°-45°) effectively accommodates target visibility in either **COL** or **PAN** mode depending on specific illumination conditions and target ranking priorities.

- Since opportunities with overlapped conditions can be acquired in **PAN** or **COL** indifferently, the choice of **HRC_MODE** will be guided by the **RANK** attribute, allowing prioritization based on scientific importance.

5.5.1.2 Region 2: High Latitudes

Region 2 (R2) consists of polar regions where **COL** conditions are never met and **PAN** conditions could become extreme (Fig. 6). This does not mean that **COL** observations are discarded. We will accept **COL** observations during the opportunity that offers the minimum incidence out of the three. HP may be critical in any case. For **PAN**, the acceptable range is extended to 90° incidence to include the N and S poles.

Figure 6. Plot of boresight longitude vs. incidence angle at high latitudes, where positive and negative incidence angles are for sun from the east and west, respectively. The green horizontal areas indicate incidence ranges ideal for COL, blue ones for PAN. Red areas indicate hot poles (HP), grey areas are for cold poles (CP).

5.5.2 STC criteria

STC targets are mainly intended for **COL** observations, as **PAN** observations are only required at the CP and for some specific targets aimed at generating higher spatial resolution DTMs (after the completion of the GM phase when the spatial resolution is slightly higher), or higher accuracy DTMs (when better illumination conditions are met). Some **PAN** observations could be requested for multi-angles target observations requesting specific off-pointing maneuvers.

Periside:

STC_MTA = 135-225. APH observations. The first opportunity available for a given target will always be selected giving priority to **COL** observations, in second priority **PAN** stereo observations to improve spatial resolution with respect the GM (after the GM the spatial resolution of the images will be slightly higher).

STC_MTA = 90-270. Mainly **COL** observations.

Aposide:

STC_MTA = 45-90;270-315 . Mainly **PAN** observations devoted to cover the CP with the illumination conditions better than during the GM at APH season.

5.5.3 VIHI criteria

The VIHI channels will always observe with priority at the first opportunity available in APH season and PHE season regardless of the latitude within the allocated resources. The selection criteria will be always related to the MTA:

Periside:

- **VIHI_MTA = 135-225. APH observations.** The first opportunity available for a given target will always be selected.

Aposide:

- **VIHI_MTA = 315-45 and VIHI_MODE = SPT.** The first opportunity available for a given target will always be selected.
- **VIHI_MTA = 315-45;135-225 and VIHI_MODE = THM.** The targets indicated will be observed at both APH and PHE seasons.

All Season Observations:

- **VIHI_MTA = 0-360.** The target will be observed at every opportunity. This conditions applies to all targets of **CATEGORY = TERRAINS** and all targets of **TYPE = PSR CRATER**.

5.6 Target Ranking

Target ranking is needed to manage operation planning tuning to fit within allocated resources, including data volume, data production profile, power, energy, number of telecommands.

A scientific rank is given in the TL for each target (i.e., **RANK** in Tab. 2) indicating the scientific relevance as described in [RD.2]. Specifically, for SIMBIO-SYS:

RANK 1: Lowest priority – well-known targets, already imaged by MESSENGER/MDIS multiple times in different conditions.

RANK 2: Low priority – well-known targets, already imaged by MESSENGER/MDIS.

RANK 3: Medium priority – targets that need further investigation or different resolution or illumination conditions than MESSENGER/MDIS products.

RANK 4: High priority – targets that address major TMX questions and need further investigation and have suboptimal coverage by MESSENGER/MDIS.

RANK 5: Highest priority – top priority targets that were never imaged before with SIMBIO-SYS resolution ranges and address pivotal TMX questions.

Additional operational ranking (to be implemented) can be based on observation quality, including the possibility to meet the best observation conditions and the expected SNR, availability of

- Include previously excluded high-priority targets.
- Expand observational coverage to wider contextual areas.
- Optimize imaging resolution and manage data volume dynamically.
- Incorporate new scientifically relevant targets identified from GM data.

Adhering to these strategic guidelines will maximize the scientific output and efficiency of HRIC observations throughout the mission.

The ideal observing conditions are resumed in table 5. The best season to observe a target can be resumed as shown in figure 7 below.

TABLE 5. HRIC_MODE vs. PLANNING REGIONS

	HRIC_MODE	
	PAN	COL
REGION 1	40°-85°	0°-45°
REGION 2	40°-90°	40°-90°

Figure 7. Maps of preferred seasons for observing in PAN or COL obtained via georeferentiation of HRIC boresight points with 1 second step covering two HY (i.e., 1 Mercury solar day). Highest resolution opportunities are on top. Region 2 (i.e., the polar regions) can only offer extreme incidence angles, therefore no distinction between PAN/COL ideal conditions is represented in the map. APH: aphelion, D2Np: day-to-night periside, D2Na: day-to-night aposide, PH: perihelion, N2Da: night-to-day aposide, N2Dp: nigh-to-day periside.

6.2 STC

Taking into account the previously stated considerations, we can now outline some essential guidelines for the formulation of an operative plan for STC target observations:

- **Priority to col observations:** The multi-filter observations will have the priority within the ranges of the APH season (MTA = 135°-225°). Both considering the opportunities during the GM (skipped orbits) and also during the specific APH devoted to the targeting phase. Larger ranges of opportunities as 90-270 will be also considered for COL observations.

- **Cold Poles Targets:** These regions will be covered in **PAN** mode considering the best illumination conditions encountered.
- **DTMs improvement:** Aphelia (MTA = 135°-225°) and Aposide ranges (45-90;270-315) will be considered to improve the DTMs both in terms of spatial resolution and in terms of vertical accuracy. Generally, the spatial resolution will increase as the mission progresses. At the same time, the vertical accuracy improves when the optimal illumination conditions for stereo reconstruction (i.e., incidence angles of 35°-75°) are met.

Target-Planning Optimization: The planning of STC targets requires the optimization of allocated resources (primarily DV, Power, and the number of TLC per day). In order to define a strategy for target selection and develop a detailed observation plan, it is necessary to adopt a heuristic approach that takes into account also the following aspects:

- Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR);
- Science Ranking;
- Imaging resolution over the mission timeline (e.g., increasing resolution, opportunities during GM or later phases);
- Maximization of spatial coverage over time.

6.3 VIHI

Given the considerations expressed above, we can briefly summarize some guidelines for the production of an Operative Plan:

Planning with Seasonal Phase. The major parameter for planning observations is the seasonal phase (VIHI_MTA). For targets selected in more than one APH or PHE season, the first opportunity will always be selected. All targets with no specific phase (0-360) will be observed at all opportunities.

Target Ranking. For the time being the Scientific Rank parameter will be the major discriminating parameter as far as resources, of any nature, are concerned.

However, it must be pointed out that a complete operative plan will require some additional interactions between science need and operative capabilities. To achieve that, we reserve the possibility to define an additional Ranking which correlate scientific relevance to observation quality. This new Ranking will provide the ultimate parameter which will allow a firm Operative Plan to be issued.

Operational Flexibility and Resource Management. Whenever additional resources should become available at MTP or STP levels, the Operative Plan shall be updated to:

- Include previously excluded high-priority targets.
- Expand observational coverage to wider contextual areas.
- Optimize imaging resolution and manage data volume dynamically.
- Incorporate new scientifically relevant targets identified from GM data.

7 Appendix

7.1 HRIC off-pointing for target longitude coverage

The selected strategy to allow full coverage of a target is to check how the ground tracks are distributed in following passages on the same area; these passages occur every 2 HY, allowing the same illumination conditions and MTA. To be noted that the gap in longitude coverage only occurs while in periside and within a latitude range of about $\pm 55^\circ$. Additionally, due to the lowering of perihelion, the issue becomes more and more critical with time, as the swath reduces while the ground tracks separation remain constant. **This implies the need to start HRIC high resolution observation of targets from the passage at APHO**, allowing to complete their longitude coverage within 5 HY, already in the extended mission. Any delay would probably result in incomplete target coverage.

Due to the effects of the WOL, orbit predictions shall be verified at the beginning of each periside season (when the Mercury dayside is on MPO's orbit periside). To fine tune the track distribution on the surface, a fixed pointing offset in roll shall be introduced at MTA=90 and MTA=180 (after flip), going back to nadir at MTA=270.

The amplitude of the offset shall be determined based on the following:

- The ground tracks of the new phase shall be such that the HRIC swaths of the new and old phases overlap.
- The minimum overlap shall be 5% of the swath (10% would be preferred, but may be not possible due to the quite reduced margins to complete the coverage with three passages).

Examples of non-optimised and optimised ground tracks are given below: the first figure shows the condition in which the third passage almost completely overlaps with the first one, leaving a gap in coverage. The following figure shows a better distribution of the ground tracks with full coverage.

It must be pointed out that this off-pointing approach does not affect the other channels objectives as the offset is maintained constant for a full season.

7.2 HRIC Stereo-DTM Strategy

For selected targets requiring high-resolution DTMs, the HRIC channel can acquire stereo image pairs under specific geometrical and operational constraints. The following strategic considerations apply:

1. Stereo Acquisition Geometry

HRIC stereo pairs can be acquired through two main strategies:

- *Intra-orbit stereo*: performed within the same orbit by applying a pitch tilt maneuver between successive acquisitions.
- *Inter-orbit stereo*: performed across different orbits by applying a roll tilt to acquire the target from a different viewing angle on subsequent passes.

2. Conflicts with Other Payload Operations

Both pitch and roll off-nadir geometries deviate from the nominal nadir-pointing configuration, potentially introducing conflicts with other remote sensing instruments—particularly BELA—which require precise nadir alignment for optimal performance.

3. Constraints During the First Nominal Year

During the initial nominal mission phase, HRIC stereo acquisitions from periside are particularly challenging. This is due to the conflicting need to prioritize nadir-pointing high-resolution coverage of target areas, making the availability of off-nadir opportunities extremely limited.

4. Advantages and Limitations of Aposide Stereo

Aposide stereo observations offer a partial mitigation to the above constraints by enabling more relaxed planning windows. However, limitations due to power availability and thermal constraints—especially near perihelion—still pose a challenge to the implementation of multiple off-nadir acquisitions.

5. Cross-MTA Stereo Opportunities

In some cases, stereo pairs may be constructed by combining observations acquired at different Mercury True Anomaly (MTA) ranges, provided that the angular separation between the observations satisfies stereo imaging criteria (e.g., sufficient variation in incidence angle and acceptable spatial resolution match). This strategy can expand stereo coverage where operational constraints prevent traditional pair acquisitions.

These strategies shall be considered on a case-by-case basis, balancing the scientific need for high-resolution DTMs against resource availability, operational limitations, and synergy with the rest of the payload. In light of these considerations, we reserve the possibility to introduce in future an additional observation mode, tentatively named **DTM**, to explicitly identify targets that require stereo acquisition strategies for Digital Terrain Model generation.

8 Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge support by the ASI-INAF agreement n. 2024-18-HH.0.